

INDIA, A SHINING STAR IS RISING IN THE GLOBAL ORBIT OF POWER: BALANCING US

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Many are wondering in spite of shared values and being the largest democracies in the world why an alliance between them has not been scripted yet. In international politics this does not happen as one wish. In the thaw of cold war after the end of the Second World War India was looked upon by both the United States and former Soviet Union for different reasons. America wanted India to be a client state to kowtow to the former's global war against Soviet communism (including China's as it was then a client state of Soviet Union). Soviet Union wanted India as a power of support in South Asia. In view of Nehru's leftist and socialistic ideology Soviet Union thought India could soft peddle communism to South Asia and even Asian continent. Further it could bolster up Soviet stand at the international level against capitalism and liberal economy. India was too large a country to be piggybacked by America in its foreign policy journey. Being a multi religious and pluralistic country to expect dedication, one voice and unquestioned support from India was a herculean task. Being a large democratic and newly independent country India cannot be expected to genuflect before America on every issue in global politics without debate and dialogue. Under Nehru India was too ambitious to follow any country or join any military alliance of super powers; it was seeking to carve out a proper niche in global politics as per its great civilization though it was disproportionate to its economy and technological development by vouchsafing for NAM among the South Countries. Love for freedom sovereignty and independence were so sacrosanct for India that these cannot be sacrificed at the altar of satisfying a foreign power. For these reasons US abstained itself from courting the friendship of India in American terms at a time when Gandhi and Nehru were lambasted as imperialistic dogs in Soviet News papers.

On the other hand, Pakistan was small country newly partitioned from India and the latter was its arch enemy as it is today. In its war against India on Kashmir issue Pakistan was in need of a super power's military, diplomatic, economic and technological support against India. It took no time in signing its joining in the CENTO military alliance led by US. The feeling of being insecure at the Indian hands and though it was a nightmare to expect India handover Kashmir to Pakistan by the pressure of America and China, the ambitious Kashmir design drew Pakistan into the embrace of America. At the same time when India was too big to be fit into cold war strategic procrustean bed of America Pakistan's geo strategic location and its over enthusiasm to jump into American bandwagon and its willingness to allow its sovereignty and territory to be used by America as military bases against former Soviet Union prompted America immediately to make Pakistan a prey of its global strategy. What played a key thinking by US policy makers is the fact that Pakistan being an Islamic country belongs to same Abraham religion as Christian religion is. Both are monolithic having one God, one prophet and one scripture unlike Hindus who have multiple gods, cults, beliefs and scriptures. For these reasons, Pakistan can be undoubtedly relied upon in its loyalty, dedication and allegiance to America. Pakistan played reliably a mediating role in bringing a rapprochement between US and China in the height of cold war by arranging a secret trip of Henry Kissinger, American secretary of state to Peking via Islamabad. America stood by Pakistan its 1948, 1965, 1971 and Kargil wars against India by military, economic and diplomatic means. In the United Nations Security Council Resolutions it used veto powers against India. When China was with Soviet Union in 1962 war between India and China India sought help from America but the latter showed a deaf ear to India except providing some spare parts to India's damaged fighter planes. America and China helped clandestinely Pakistan produce nuclear weapons but when India produced nuclear weapons in 1998 under the leadership of Vajpayee the then Prime Minister of India America used sanctions against India. Pressler amendment act was passed by American congress to put restrictions on India that these cannot be used against Pakistan. Whereas following India when Pakistan exploded nuclear weapons no sanction was used against Pakistan and no condition on it was put by US that these could not be used against India. This kind of duplicity and double standard in US foreign policy was very much known to India and a strong belief in its mind has been persistent that US could be a reliable partner and to be believed will be a diplomatic blunder. When India was bringing to the notice of the world powers and alleging that Pakistan has been sponsoring terrorism till today was given a bluff by America. But when there was 9/11

terrorist attack on America, it immediately started supporting India against world terrorism. The tendency of America has been always to hyphen India with Pakistan. It has never differentiated between the victim and the perpetrator of the crime. In all above cited wars, conflict and terrorism American has tried to hyphen India with Pakistan. With the end of the cold war in 1990 it was hoped that in American foreign policy will usher in a dehyphenated attitude while dealing with India and Pakistan. Nothing of the sort happened. In case of Ukraine war between Russia and Ukraine the role of US reflects and stands a witness to its policy of duplicity. India has been importing oil from Russia to the chagrin of America. Sanctions were exerted on India but the latter did pay a lip service to Trump administration. Many European countries are also importing natural gas and oil from Russia but no sanction on them by America. During India's operation of Sindoo under the leadership of Modi in retaliation to Pakistani sponsored terrorist attack and killing of 40 Hindus at Pahalgam in Kashmir the role of Trump. American president was credited with the same American duplicity and double standard leaning towards and associated with Pakistan. Trump waged a tariff war against India. In its conduct of foreign policy Trump has been erratic and sometimes he used to praise Modi in tall words and the next time he is seen praising Pakistan and turning against India. How a president can be relied when his words are tossing against each other?

On the other hand, former Soviet Union and present Russia has been very friendly and reliable to India. Along with trade and business, it has been a major supplier of weapons fighter jets fulfilling the military and defense requirements of India. In has used veto power in Security Council against US in support of India. It signed a treaty of friendship and cooperation with India in the wake of 1971 war against Pakistan. Russia and India are members of BRICS. A new alliance between India China and Russia has come up.

When Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi met with US President Joe Biden in the White House this month, many observers saw the makings of an evolving alliance against China. But such expectations are over nurtured. As Indian Foreign Minister Jaishankar has made it crystal clear, a formal alliance is not in the cards, even if it is still possible to maintain long-term partnerships in a multipolar world of "frenemies."

Post colonial mistrust

As analyzed above India has a long history of post-colonial mistrust of alliances. But it has also long been preoccupied with China, at least since the Himalayas border war the two countries fought in 1962. While serving in President Jimmy Carter's administration, Joseph

S Nye JrI was sent to India to encourage Prime Minister Morarji Desai to support a South Asian nuclear-weapons-free zone, lest the burgeoning nuclear race between India and Pakistan get out of hand. As the Indian hosts told him at the time, they wanted to be compared not to Pakistan in South Asia, but to China in East Asia. This shows American persistent with its long followed policy of hyphenating India with Pakistan a terrorist war mongering and unreliable country except that it has become an all weather friend of America ignoring India's credentials of being a great democratic country and a great civilization and a reliable peace loving nations and underestimating India's growing security concerns from nuclear China and Pakistan.

After the terrorist attacks of September 11, 2001, the United States and India began 20 years of annual "Track Two" talks between former diplomats who were still in close contact with those in government. (The American delegation, for example, included figures such as Henry Kissinger and Richard Holbrooke.) The Indian participants shared their US counterparts' concerns about al-Qaeda and other extremist threats in Afghanistan and Pakistan, but they also made clear that they objected and raised serious concerns to the Americans' tendency to think about India and Pakistan as "linked by a hyphen." The established American policy of the link between aid and influence has been used at present by Trump administration.

India's galloping economy

The Indians were also concerned about China, but according to America India wanted to maintain the appearance of good relations – and access to the Chinese market. China has long been one of India's largest trading partners, but its economy has grown much more rapidly than India's. Using market exchange rates, China represented 3.6% of world GDP by the turn of this century, but India did not reach that level until the 2020s. At present China's economy has started declining. India has become the 4th largest economy in the world. It next two years it is going to be the third largest economy. Its GDP is higher than America and even China. India's GDP stands at 7.8.

In the 2000s, as China's growth far outpaced theirs, the Indians in the Track Two talks worried not just about China's support for Pakistan, but also about its increasing global power more broadly. As one Indian strategist put it, "We have decided we dislike you less than we dislike China" – and this was long before the 2020 skirmish on the disputed Himalayan border.

QUAD agreement between US and India

The India-US alignment has since strengthened considerably. A decade ago, the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue (“Quad”) meetings between US, Indian, Japanese, and Australian diplomats were downplayed; now, they are loudly publicized and held at the head-of-government level.

America ignoring its own history of diplomacy

India today holds more joint military exercises with the US than with any other country. But this arrangement is a far cry from an alliance. India still imports over half its arms from Russia, is a major buyer of sanctioned Russian oil (alongside China), and frequently votes against the US at the United Nations. Indeed, India has focused on peace and cessation of war in the context of 2022 invasion of Ukraine Modi has always stressed on the fact that there is no alternative to peace. War is not the instrument to resolve conflict. It has been alleged that India has failed failed to condemn the Soviet invasion of Afghanistan in 1979. For all of India’s self-congratulation as the world’s largest democracy, it has not come to the defense of democratic Ukraine. Its top priorities are to maintain its access to arms and oil, and to avoid pushing Russia further into China’s arms. India has understood that America has been equally accused of military intervention into many states like Iraq, Syria, Libya Afghanistan and many others. America has closed its eyes to its own history of diplomacy. It has been constantly supporting the dictatorial, military and terrorist regimes against the democratic states. It stood with a military dictatorial state Pakistan against a democratic regime India in 1971 war. Not until it was attacked by the same terrorist in 9/11 incident, America spoke against terrorism. It has always been with Pakistan even today.

Though Biden has invited Modi to both of his Summits for Democracy, there is no shortage of Western and Indian critics who have decried Modi’s illiberal turn toward Hindu nationalism. This criticism is a reflection of pre-colonial and post colonial grand narrative going on by the liberal and leftist gang to break India into pieces and to demonize the great Indian civilization and history of India by denouncing its ancient education system and sanatan dharma by converting Hindus into Christian and Islamic religion through missionaries and NGOs and to create division among various castes by misinterpreting its history and literature. Through the instrumentalities of human rights foreign aid like US Aid, Ford foundation and deep state, Bharat was denounced in its essence and profundity. Secularism was made to be understood at all levels anti Hinduism. Modi’s rise has been hailed as a symptom of rescuing Bharat from the dungeon into which all western forces in

alliance with leftist and liberal elements have been trying for the last decades and centuries to throw. The critics voice is the voice of these disruptive elements acting against India. Under the stubborn and determined and strong leadership of Modi India in world politics speaks from a position of strength and power. In this respect, India's importance is growing. Earlier this year, it surpassed China as the world's most populous country. As its population has grown to 1.4 billion, China has been experiencing demographic decline, with a labor force that peaked. Moreover, India's economy is on track to expand by 6% this year – faster than China's – making it the world's become the third largest economy surpassing EU very soon.

Conclusion

With a huge population, nuclear weapons, a large army, a growing labor force, strong elite education, a culture of entrepreneurialism, and links to a large and influential diaspora, India will remain a significant factor in the global balance of power. But one should not get carried away. India alone cannot balance China, which got a big head start in its development. India's growing economy is not to be underestimated. Its almost self reliance in defense production and many other weapons have propelled China to take seriously. The way America demonstrates its overweening interest in having strengthened relationship with India attests to the fact that India is growing and moving very speedily within a short time under the leadership of Modi with his clear and foresighted vision and roadmap to be the *Viswa guru* (the guru of the world). There has been a remarkable reduction in the number of poverty stricken people in India. Despite the selective decoupling of trade in key strategic sectors, India still does not want to forego access to the Chinese market. While it participates in the Quad, it also participates in the Shanghai Cooperation Organization and the periodic meetings of the BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa). Although it no longer speaks of non-alignment, nor is it interested in restrictive alliances. Following the basic logic of balance-of-power politics, India and the US seem fated not for marriage but for a long-term partnership – one that might last only as long as both countries remain concerned about China. But to America's great regret, President Trump is spoiling the broth by his unsteady, uncertain and opaque vision about the future configuration of powers in global politics.

References

Jaishankar Subrahmanyam, The Indian way Harper Collins Publishers India 2020

Editors, World Politics Review, Can Modi deliver for India? June 25 2024.

*US –Japan- India Track- two, Strategic Dialogue May 17-19, 2013, Apen
Institute India.*

*Malhotra Rajiv and Aravindan Neelakanadan, Breaking India: Western Interventions in Dravidian
and Dalit Faultlines, 2011. New Delhi: Amaryllis*